

Predominant spastic paraparesis associated with the D178N mutation in *PRNP*

Genetic analyses

Genomic DNA was extracted from blood, extracted DNA was converted to sequencing libraries using a PCR-free paired-end protocol (Illumina TruSeq). Sequencing was performed on the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platforms aiming at 30x median coverage. Data was aligned to GRCh37 and processed with the bioinformatics pipeline MIP v6.0.17. Variants were visualized and reviewed in Scout with an *in-silico* panel consisting of 109 genes, associated with adult lipofuscinosis, neurodegeneration, and motor neuron disease. Included genes were: *ALS2, ANG, ANXA11, APP, AR, ATN1, ATP13A2, ATP1A3, ATXN1, ATXN10, ATXN2, ATXN3, C19orf12, C9orf72, CCNF, CHCHD10, CHMP2B, CLN1, CLN3, CLN5, CLN6, CSF1R, CTSD, CTSF, DAO, DCTN1, DNAJC5, DNAJC6, DNMT1, EPHA4, EPM2A, ERBB4, FBXO7, FIG4, FTL, FUS, GBA, GCH1, GLE1, GRN, HNRNPA1, HNRNPA2B1, HTT, ITM2B, JPH3, LRRK2, LYST, MAPT, MATR3, MME, NEF4, NEFH, NEK1, NHLRC1, NOP56, NOTCH3, OPA3, OPTN, PANK2, PARK7, PFN1, PINK1, PLA2G6, PLD3, PON1, PON2, PON3, PPARGC1A, PPP2R2B, PPT1, PRKN, PRKRA, PRNP, PRPH, PSEN1, PSEN2, RAB39B, SETX, SIGMAR1, SLC30A10, SLC39A14, SLC52A2, SLC52A3, SLC6A3, SNCA, SOD1, SORL1, SPG11, SPR, SQSTM1, SYNJ1, TAF15, TARDBP, TBK1, TBP, TH, TMEM106b, TREM2, TUBA4A, TUBB4A, TYROBP, UBE3A, UBQLN2, UNC13A, VAPB, VCP, VPS13A, VPS35, WDR45.* Possible C9orf72-repeat expansion was also analyzed from the data and found to be normal. The D178N variant in PRNP was confirmed by secondary method at an external genetic laboratory (Blueprint Genetics, Finland).

Western blot

Western blotting / Sodium phosphotungstic acid (NaPTA) analysis was performed using the SUPERSIGNAL detection system and the development System XRS+ Bio-Rad. This case was initially PrP negative on a standard diagnostic Western Blot and centrifugal concentration (200ul). NaPTA Western Blot analysis showed detectable levels of the protease-resistant prion protein

fragment in the frontal cortex (only tissue available for biochemical analysis). The isoform pattern showed abundance of the di-glycosylated band with a non-glycosylated band with a molecular mass of around 19kDa, suggestive of a "type 2B" isoform. Low levels of PrPres, and PrPres type 2B or 2A/B have previously been observed for FFI (D178N-129M) cases referred to NCJDRSU.

Additional references

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